

RIG-I Activation and NKG2A Editing Synergize to Enhance NK Cell Antitumor Activity.

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Supplementary Figure Legends

Supplementary Figure 1: RIG-I induced NK-cell cytotoxicity differs according to the cellular targets.

(a, b) NK cytotoxicity after 20 h of cocultures with 721.221, K-562, PANC-1, A549, Caco-2, JEG-3 and U-2 OS cells previously stimulated with RIG-I ligand (3p-dsRNA) or control RNA (3p-ssRNA). Cocultures with expanded primary NK cells (a, Mean \pm SD specific lysis from at least 4 NK donors at different E:T ratios are shown) or NK-92 cells (b, Mean \pm SD specific lysis from at least 4 independent experiments at different E:T ratios are shown). (c) HEK-Blue IFN type-I activity in supernatants from wells with target cells alone in the cocultures, expressed as IFN α 2a equivalent units (EqU, n=4). (d) Correlation plots for IFN-I production and cytotoxicity increase for primary NK cells and NK-92 cells. (e, f, g) NK cytotoxicity after stimulation of the NK cells with RIG-I ligand (3p-dsRNA) or control RNA (3p-ssRNA). Experimental design is represented in (e), and cytotoxicity after 20 h of cocultures with Capan-2, A-431, EFO-21, HT-29, SK-OV-3, and A549 cells are shown for primary NK (f, Mean \pm SD specific lysis from at least 4 NK donors at different E:T ratios), and NK-92 cells (g, Mean \pm SD specific lysis from at least 3 independent experiments). Statistical comparisons were performed using two-way ANOVA with matched donors and Šídák's post-hoc test (a, b, f, g). *p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.

Supplementary Figure 2: The MHC-I molecule HLA-E is highly and broadly upregulated by RIG-I stimulation.

(a) PD-1 surface expression on cultured NK cells. Represented are the distribution of PD-1 NK positive cells as % of live NK cells. Dots represent independent donors (n=10). (b) High contrast image of the HLA-G immunoblotting shown in Figure 2c. (c) HLA-G and β -tubulin immunoblotting on A549, A-431, SK-OV-3, and JEG-3 cell lines after 24h stimulation with 1000 U/ml IFN γ or IFN α , or 400 ng/ml 3p-dsRNA, and medium as control. (d) mRNA expression of HLA-E, CXCL10 and IFIT1 after 17h or 4.5h (IFN α and IFN γ) of stimulation with the specified ligand (mean of 4 independent experiments \pm SD). n.d: Ct values not determined within 40 PCR cycles. (e) Table of ligands and receptors used in d. (f, g) Total HLA-E protein levels after the indicated times of stimulation with 1000 U/ml IFN γ or 400 ng/ml RIG-I ligand. Representative immunoblotting for HLA-E and β -tubulin expression (f), and flow cytometry of total HLA-E after permeabilization staining (g, mean and SEM are shown, n=4). Statistical comparisons were performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnet's test (d). *p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.

Supplementary Figure 3: HLA-E upregulation on tumor cells hinders RIG-I induced cytotoxicity by NK cells.

(a) HLA-E immunoblotting on the clones used in Figure 3a-c and Sup. Fig. 3c. (b) Flow cytometry expression of surface HLA-E on target cells alone stimulated with 0.4 μ g/ml 3p-dsRNA (RIG-I ligand) or 3p-ssRNA (control RNA), measured after the cocultures with primary NK cells shown in Figure 3a and Sup. Fig. 3c. (c) Twenty-hour NK cytotoxicity assay on Caco-2 and A549 WT and HLA-E $^{-/-}$ cell lines previously stimulated with 1000 U/ml IFN γ or control medium for 24 h, E:T ratios 5:1 measured with primary NK cells (n=7 and n=3 NK donors for A549 and Caco-2, respectively). (d-h) Cytotoxicity on target cells previously stimulated with 1000U/m IFN γ or control medium. Surface HLA-E expression on target cells alone was quantified by flow cytometry after cocultures (d), and specific lysis measured on Capan-2, EFO-21, PANC-1, JEG-3, U-2 OS, Caco-2, and HT-29 with primary NK cells (e, n \geq 4 donors) or NK-92 (f, n \geq 3 independent experiments). Cytotoxicity on 721.221 and K-562 was also quantified after IFN γ stimulation with primary NK cells (g) and NK-92 cells (h). (i-k) Cytotoxicity on tumor cells transduced with lentiviral particles expressing HLA-E alleles 01:01, or 01:03, followed by IRES-GFP (lentivirus #1), or IRES-GFP-2PA-Puromycin sequences (lentivirus #2), or a lentivirus control expressing only GFP or GFP-2PA-Puromycin (EV). Cells were cocultured with primary NK cells (i, n \geq 4 donors) or NK-92 (j, n \geq 2 independent experiments). (k) HLA-E surface expression of the transduced cells used in i, j and Fig. 3d. Statistical comparisons were performed using

two-way ANOVA with matched values and Šídák's (b, c, e-h) or Dunnett's (i-k) post-hoc test, or a paired t test (d). *p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.

Supplementary Figure 4: Paired guide RNA CRISPR-Cas9 generates efficient NKG2A deletion on primary NK cells.

(a) Gating strategy used to analyze NKG2A expression on NK cells in Fig. 4a. (b) Representation of the paired guide RNA CRISPR-Cas9 chosen and used for editing of the NKG2A gene in this study. (c) Agarose gel from PCR of genomic DNA from electroporated primary NK cells with RNP containing a -CTRg or the 2 NKG2A gRNA (n=4 donors are shown). (d-f) Indel decomposition analysis by TIDE is shown for 3 donors electroporated with guides #1, #2 or paired-guides #1+#2. (g) Summary table of the observed indels and total efficiency leading to in-frame ($\Sigma(\text{WT}/-3)$) and out-of-frame mutations in the NKG2A gene ($\Sigma(\text{Frameshift})$) in the same donors shown in Fig. 4c. (h) Gating strategy used to define NK cell population in cocultures with the B cell line 721.221 in the Fig. 4e. (i, j) Cytotoxicity of NKG2A-edited primary NK cells in 20h cocultures with the indicated cell lines. NKG2A surface expression on the primary NK cells from control wells with NK alone is shown (i, from Fig. 4f, Sup. Fig. 4j), and HT-29 specific lysis measured by flow cytometry in cocultures with primary NK cells (l, shown are mean \pm SD from 4 donors). (k) IFN γ measured by ELISA in supernatants from cocultures of HT-29 cells with gene-edited primary NK cells (n=4 donors). (l-n) NKG2A expression was analyzed by flow cytometry on genome-edited NK-92 cells (l, mean \pm SD from 6 independent experiments), as well as their IFN γ production (m) and cytotoxic effect on SK-OV-3, EFO-21, Capan-2, A549, A-431, PANC-1 and U-2 OS (n, mean \pm SD from at least 3 independent experiments) after 20h cocultures. Statistical comparisons were performed using paired t-test (i, l), or two-way ANOVA followed by multiple comparisons by Šídák's post-hoc test (j, k, m, n). *p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.

Supplementary Figure 5: NKG2A-edited primary NK cells exhibited increased cytotoxicity, further enhanced by RIG-I stimulation.

(a) Surface expression of NKG2A and HLA-E on the surface of NK cells or target cells alone was measured by flow cytometry on control wells from experiments in Fig. 5a, and Sup. Fig. 5b. (b) Cytotoxicity of the NKG2A-edited primary NK cells in combination with RIG-I stimulation of the target cells (Capan-2, mean and SD from n=5 donors). (c-d) Cocultures of RIG-I stimulated target cells and NKG2A- edited NK-92 cells. Target cells were stimulated 24 h before cocultures with 0.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ RIG-I ligand (3p-dsRNA) or control RNA (3p-ssRNA), and NKG2A and HLA-E expression were measured in control wells where only NK-92 or target cells were present (c), and specific lysis was measured by flow cytometry against A549 (d, Mean \pm SD specific lysis from 2 independent experiments at different E:T ratios are shown). Statistical comparisons were performed using paired t

test for surface expression of HLA-E and NKG2A (a, c) or two-way ANOVA with matched donors and Tukey's post-hoc test (b, d). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.005$, **** $p < 0.001$.

Supplementary Figure 6: Synergistic cytotoxicity of NKG2A-edited NK cells and RIG-I stimulation is independent of donor/tumor KIR-matching.

(a) Cytotoxicity of NKG2A-edited primary NK cells with KIR match, or mismatch during 20 h of cocultures with A549 cells (n=5 donors with KIR match, and n=5 donors with KIR MM). (b) NKG2A and KIR surface expression measured by flow cytometry on NK cells used in the cocultures in Fig. 6b, c, and Sup. Fig. 6a (n=18 donors). (c) 20 h cytotoxicity of -CTRg electroporated NK cells, data from the cocultures in Fig. 6b, and Sup. Fig. 6a (n= 5 KIR match donors and 5 KIR MM donors for A549 and Capan-2 cell lines, n= 4 KIR match donors and 4 KIR MM donors for A-431). (d) Schematic representation of the KIR MM definition for single MM on KIR3DL1 and KIR2DL1 used on A-431 cells (KIR3DL1), and Capan-2 and A549 cells (KIR2DL1). (e) Cytotoxicity of NK cells with a KIR MM for only the indicated KIR, and NK cells from donors with KIR matches, after 20 h cocultures with the indicated cell line. (f, g) HLA-E surface expression on target cells used in Fig. 6c, and NKG2A on NK cells with KIR matches and KIR MM, as measured in control wells from cocultures with A-431 (f, n= 8 for A-431 target cells, n=4 donors with KIR matches, and n=4 donors with KIR MM), and with Capan-2 (g, n= 9 for Capan-2 target cells, n=5 donors with KIR matches, and n=4 donors with KIR MM). Statistical comparisons were performed using two-way ANOVA with matched donors and Šídák's multiple comparisons test (a, b, c, e), or paired t test for surface expression of proteins (f, g). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.005$, **** $p < 0.001$.